

**PARAMETRIC ANISOTROPIC DOUBLE PHASE FREE
BOUNDARY PROBLEMS WITH NONLOCAL TERMS
AND CONVECTION: EXISTENCE, STABILITY
AND ASYMPTOTIC BEHAVIOR**

JINXIA CEN^{✉1,2}, LESZEK GASIŃSKI^{✉3}, CALOGERO VETRO^{✉4} AND
SHENGDA ZENG^{✉*,2,5,6}

¹School of Mathematical Sciences, Zhejiang Normal University
Jinhua 321004, China

²Guangxi Colleges and Universities Key Laboratory of Complex System Optimization and
Big Data Processing
Yulin Normal University, Yulin 537000, Guangxi, China

³Department of Mathematics, Pedagogical University of Cracow
Podchorążych 2, 30-084 Cracow, Poland

⁴University of Palermo, Department of Mathematics and Computer Science
Via Archirafi 34, 90123 Palermo, Italy

⁵Department of Mathematics, Nanjing University
Nanjing, Jiangsu 210093, China

⁶Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science
ul. Łojasiewicza 6, 30-348 Krakow, Poland

*Dedicated to Professor Vicențiu D. Rădulescu
on the occasion of his 65th birthday.*

ABSTRACT. This paper is concerned with the study of a parametric anisotropic double phase free boundary problem (DPFBP, for short) involving $(p(\cdot), q(\cdot))$ -Laplacian, convection term (a reaction term depending on the gradient), and two parameters (θ, λ) appearing in $q(\cdot)$ -Laplacian and convection term, respectively. The $(p(\cdot), q(\cdot))$ -Laplace operator in (DPFBP) is considered to be controlled by two highly nonlinear and nonlocal functions. First, we apply a surjectivity theorem for pseudomonotone operators with a maximal monotone perturbation and the theory of nonsmooth analysis to examine the nonemptiness and compactness of weak solution set to (DPFBP). Then, we explore the asymptotic behavior of solution set to (DPFBP), as the parameters θ and λ vary in appropriate ranges. Finally, a stability result to (DPFBP) is provided, when the obstacle function is approximated by a convergent sequence.

2020 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 35J20, 35J25, 35R35, 35J60, 49J52.

Key words and phrases. Anisotropic double phase free boundary problem, $(p(\cdot), q(\cdot))$ -Laplacian, convection term, existence and compactness, asymptotic behavior, stability.

*Corresponding author: Shengda Zeng.

1. Introduction. Given a bounded domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^N$ with $N \geq 2$ and smooth boundary $\partial\Omega$, and two continuous functions $p, q: \Omega \rightarrow (1, +\infty)$ such that $q \neq p$ and $q(x) \leq p(x)$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, two nonlocal functions $N: L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ and $M: L^{q^*(\cdot)}(\Omega) \times [0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$, and an obstacle function $\Phi: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ (without loss any generality, we suppose that $\Phi(x) \geq 0$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$), we are interesting in the investigation of the following complicated parametric anisotropic double phase free boundary problem involving $(p(\cdot), q(\cdot))$ -Laplace operator, nonlocal functions and convection term

$$\begin{aligned} -N(u)\Delta_{p(\cdot)}u - M(u, \theta)\Delta_{q(\cdot)}u - \lambda f(x, u, \nabla u) &= Z(x) && \text{in } \Omega, \\ Z(x) \geq 0, \quad u(x) \leq \Phi(x), \text{ and } Z(x)(u(x) - \Phi(x)) &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega, \\ u &= 0 && \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda \in (0, +\infty)$, $\theta \in [0, +\infty)$, and $\Delta_{p(\cdot)}$ stands for the $p(\cdot)$ -Laplacian given by

$$\Delta_{p(\cdot)}u = \operatorname{div} \left(|\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u \right) \quad \text{for all } u \in W^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega),$$

with $W^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ being the variable exponent Sobolev space, and $f: \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a Carathéodory function (i.e., $\Omega \ni x \mapsto f(x, s, \xi) \in \mathbb{R}$ is measurable in Ω for all $(s, \xi) \in \mathbb{R}^{N+1}$ and $\mathbb{R}^{N+1} \ni (s, \xi) \mapsto f(x, s, \xi) \in \mathbb{R}$ is continuous for a.e. $x \in \Omega$) which will be specialized in Section 3.

On the one hand, it is not difficult to see that problem (1) can be rewritten equivalently to the following formulation

$$\begin{aligned} \min \left\{ -N(u)\Delta_{p(\cdot)}u - M(u, \theta)\Delta_{q(\cdot)}u - \lambda f(x, u, \nabla u), \Phi(x) - u(x) \right\} &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega, \\ u &= 0 && \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we can observe that problem (1) contains several interesting special cases:

- (i) If p and q are two constants, i.e., $1 < q < p$, then problem (1) reduces to the following parametric isotropic double phase free boundary problem

$$\begin{aligned} -N(u)\Delta_p u - M(u, \theta)\Delta_q u - \lambda f(x, u, \nabla u) &= Z(x) && \text{in } \Omega, \\ Z(x) \geq 0, \quad u(x) \leq \Phi(x), \text{ and } Z(x)(u(x) - \Phi(x)) &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega, \\ u &= 0 && \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with $\Delta_p u = \operatorname{div} (|\nabla u|^{p-2} \nabla u)$ for all $u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega)$. This problem was discussed by Liu-Zeng-Gasiński-Kim [20], when M is a constant.

- (ii) If $\Phi \equiv +\infty$, then problem (1) becomes the following parametric anisotropic double phase boundary value problem with nonlocal functions and convection term:

$$\begin{aligned} -N(u)\Delta_{p(\cdot)}u - M(u, \theta)\Delta_{q(\cdot)}u - \lambda f(x, u, \nabla u) &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega, \\ u &= 0 && \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In fact, problem (3) has been considered by Vetro-Winkert [34], when N and M are independent of u and θ .

The main goal of the paper is threefold. The first goal of this paper is to establish the existence of weak solutions of problem (1) and to prove the compactness of weak solution set to problem (1). The second aim of this paper is to explore the asymptotic behavior of solution set of problem (1) when the parameters, appearing in $q(\cdot)$ -Laplacian and convection term, range in appropriate domains. However, the

last intention of this paper is to study the stability result to the weak solution set of problem (1) as the obstacle function is approximated by a convergent sequence.

Observe that the free boundary variational problem under consideration, namely problem (1), pertains to the study of nonlinear elastic contact mechanics problems for anisotropic materials, because such problem combines the following interesting and challenging phenomena in a problem:

- a nonlinear and nonhomogeneous anisotropic differential operator, i.e., $(p(\cdot), q(\cdot))$ -Laplace operator;
- a nonlinear convection term;
- two parameters appearing in $q(\cdot)$ -Laplacian, $\Delta_{q(\cdot)}$, and nonlinear convection term f , respectively;
- two highly nonlinear and nonlocal terms N and M to control the $p(\cdot)$ -Laplacian and $q(\cdot)$ -Laplacian, respectively;
- a complementary condition, thus, free boundary condition.

From the physical point of view, the $(p(\cdot), q(\cdot))$ -Laplacian can describe precisely the deformation characteristic of the elastic body which is made by mixed materials with different strength and stiffness. Motivated by such reason, various anisotropic equations with competition phenomena in the source, were studied recently by Byun-Ko [4], Saoudi-Ghanmi [33] (equations driven by the $p(\cdot)$ -Laplacian), Salmani [32] (equations driven by a Leray-Lions operator) and by Papageorgiou-Rădulescu-Zhang [27], Papageorgiou-Winkert [29], Papageorgiou-Rădulescu-Repovš [26], Rădulescu [30], Mingione-Rădulescu [24], Liu-Papageorgiou [19], Bahrouni-Rădulescu-Repovš [2] (equations driven by the $(p(\cdot), q(\cdot))$ -Laplacian). Furthermore, free boundary variational problems in obstacle problems can be found in physics, biology, and mathematical finance, for example, the well-known financial challenges is establishing the arbitrage-free price of American-style options. Concerning the mathematical analysis of free boundary variational problems with obstacles, we refer to the recent contributions of Liu et al. [16], Carl-Le-Winkert [5], Iannizzotto-Papageorgiou [14], Migórski-Khan-Zeng [22, 23], Liu-Migórski-Nguyen-Zeng [17], Zeng-Bai-Gasiński-Winkert [36, 37], Zeng-Rădulescu-Winkert [38] and so forth. Now, it is well-known that in a single or a multiphase fluid flow, the convection effect may appear spontaneously because of the combined effects of material heterogeneity and the influence of body forces on a fluid (commonly density and gravity). Whereas, the reaction terms which depend on the gradient of unknown functions can precisely model the convection effect for various fluids flow. With respect to the system with convection term, we refer to the works of Albalawi-Alharthi-Vetro [1], Faraci-Motreanu-Puglisi [8], Faraci-Puglisi [9], Figueiredo-Madeira [10], Gasiński-Papageorgiou [12], Gasiński-Winkert [13], Liu-Motreanu-Zeng [18], Marano-Winkert [21], Zeng-Bai-Gasiński [35] and Papageorgiou-Rădulescu-Repovš [25].

The remaining parts of this paper are organized as follows. Section 2 presents a detailed overview about variable exponent Lebesgue/Sobolev spaces, and a surjectivity theorem for pseudomonotone operators with a maximal monotone perturbation. Section 3 is devoted to prove the existence of a weak solution of problem (1) and to verify the compactness of solution set to problem (1). However, in Section 4, we deliver the asymptotic behavior and stability results of solution set to problem (1) when the parameters θ and λ vary in appropriate ranges, and the obstacle function Φ is approximated by a convergent sequence.

2. Preliminaries. In this section, we are going to recall some necessary results and basic notations which will be used from time to time in Sections 3 and 4. For more details, we can refer to [6, 7, 31].

Assume that $N \geq 2$ and $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^N$ is a given bounded domain such that its boundary $\Gamma := \partial\Omega$ is smooth. Let $1 \leq s < +\infty$. In what follows, we denote by $\|\cdot\|_s$ the norm of Lebesgue space $L^s(\Omega)$ (or $L^s(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^N)$) defined by

$$\|w\|_s := \left(\int_{\Omega} |w|^s dx \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} \quad \text{for all } w \in L^s(\Omega).$$

Also, by $W_0^{1,s}(\Omega) \subset \{u \in L^s(\Omega) \mid \nabla u \in L^s(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^N)\}$ we denote the Sobolev space

$$W_0^{1,s}(\Omega) := \overline{C_0^\infty(\Omega)}^{\|\cdot\|_{1,s}},$$

which endowed with the norm $\|\cdot\|_{0,s}$ given by

$$\|u\|_{0,s} := \|\nabla u\|_s \quad \text{for all } u \in W_0^{1,s}(\Omega),$$

becomes a reflexive and separable Banach space, where $\|u\|_{1,s} = \|u\|_s + \|\nabla u\|_s$ for all $u \in \{u \in L^s(\Omega) \mid \nabla u \in L^s(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^N)\}$. Throughout the whole paper, we use the notations “ \xrightarrow{w} ” and “ \rightarrow ” to stand for the weak and the strong convergence, respectively, in various function spaces. Moreover, we adopt the symbol $s' > 1$ to denote the conjugate of $s > 1$, i.e., $\frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s'} = 1$.

Let $C_+(\overline{\Omega}) \subset C(\overline{\Omega})$ be such that

$$C_+(\overline{\Omega}) := \{p \in C(\overline{\Omega}) \mid 1 < p(x) \text{ for all } x \in \overline{\Omega}\}.$$

Let $p \in C_+(\overline{\Omega})$. In the sequel, we set

$$p_- := \min_{x \in \overline{\Omega}} p(x) \quad \text{and} \quad p_+ := \max_{x \in \overline{\Omega}} p(x).$$

In the meantime, we denote by $p' \in C_+(\overline{\Omega})$ the conjugate variable exponent to p , that is,

$$\frac{1}{p(x)} + \frac{1}{p'(x)} = 1 \quad \text{for all } x \in \overline{\Omega}.$$

Whereas, the symbol p^* is the critical Sobolev variable exponent of $p \in C_+(\overline{\Omega})$ defined by

$$p^*(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{Np(x)}{N-p(x)} & \text{if } p(x) < N, \\ +\infty & \text{if } p(x) \geq N, \end{cases} \quad \text{for all } x \in \overline{\Omega}. \quad (4)$$

Next, let us move our attention to variable exponents Lebesgue and Sobolev spaces. We set $M(\Omega) := \{u \text{ is measurable in } \Omega \mid u: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\}$. The variable exponent Lebesgue space $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ is given by

$$L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) := \left\{ u \in M(\Omega) : \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p(x)} dx < +\infty \right\}.$$

It is well-known that $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ equipped with the Luxemburg norm defined by

$$\|u\|_{p(\cdot)} := \inf \left\{ \lambda > 0 : \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{|u|}{\lambda} \right)^{p(x)} dx \leq 1 \right\}$$

becomes a separable and uniformly convex (hence, reflexive) Banach space. It is not difficult to see that the dual space of $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ is $L^{p'(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and the following Hölder inequality is satisfied:

$$\int_{\Omega} |uv| \, dx \leq \left[\frac{1}{p_-} + \frac{1}{p'_-} \right] \|u\|_{p(\cdot)} \|v\|_{p'(\cdot)} \leq 2 \|u\|_{p(\cdot)} \|v\|_{p'(\cdot)}$$

for all $u \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and for all $v \in L^{p'(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Furthermore, if $p_1, p_2 \in C_+(\overline{\Omega})$ satisfy $p_1(x) \leq p_2(x)$ for all $x \in \overline{\Omega}$, then the following continuous embedding is valid

$$L^{p_2(\cdot)}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^{p_1(\cdot)}(\Omega).$$

For $p \in C_+(\overline{\Omega})$, we also introduce the modular function $\varrho_{p(\cdot)}: L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+ := [0, +\infty)$ defined by

$$\varrho_{p(\cdot)}(u) := \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p(x)} \, dx \quad \text{for all } u \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega). \quad (5)$$

We collect some important relations between the norm of $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and the modular function $\varrho_{p(\cdot)}$ by the following proposition.

Proposition 2.1. *Assume that $p \in C_+(\overline{\Omega})$ and $\{u_n, n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, then we have:*

- (i) $\|u\|_{p(\cdot)} = \lambda \iff \varrho_{p(\cdot)}\left(\frac{u}{\lambda}\right) = 1$ with $u \neq 0$;
- (ii) $\|u\|_{p(\cdot)} < 1$ (resp. $= 1, > 1$) $\iff \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(u) < 1$ (resp. $= 1, > 1$);
- (iii) $\|u\|_{p(\cdot)} < 1 \implies \|u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_+} \leq \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(u) \leq \|u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_-}$;
- (iv) $\|u\|_{p(\cdot)} > 1 \implies \|u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_-} \leq \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(u) \leq \|u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_+}$;
- (v) $\|u_n\|_{p(\cdot)} \rightarrow 0 \iff \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(u_n) \rightarrow 0$;
- (vi) $\|u_n\|_{p(\cdot)} \rightarrow +\infty \iff \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(u_n) \rightarrow +\infty$.

Further, we denote by $W^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ the variable exponent Sobolev space formulated by

$$W^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) := \left\{ u \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) : |\nabla u| \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \right\}.$$

It is well-known that $W^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ is equipped with the norm

$$\|u\|_{W^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)} := \|u\|_{p(\cdot)} + \|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)} \quad \text{for all } u \in W^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega),$$

to be a separable and reflexive Banach space, where $\|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)} := \|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}$. Additionally, we define

$$W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) = \overline{C_0^\infty(\Omega)}^{\|\cdot\|_{W^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)}}.$$

From Poincaré's inequality, we know that we can endow the space $W_0^{1,r(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ with the equivalent norm

$$\|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)} = \|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)} \quad \text{for all } u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega).$$

Also, we denote by $C^{0, \frac{1}{|\log t|}}(\bar{\Omega})$ the set of all functions $p: \bar{\Omega} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that are log-Hölder continuous, i.e., there exists a constant $C > 0$ satisfying

$$|p(x) - p(y)| \leq \frac{C}{|\log |x - y||} \quad \text{for all } x, y \in \bar{\Omega} \text{ with } |x - y| < \frac{1}{2}.$$

The following proposition gives several important embeddings results, its detailed proof can be found in Diening-Harjulehto-Hästö-Ružička [6, Corollary 8.3.2] and Fan [7, Propositions 2.1 and 2.2].

Proposition 2.2. *The following statements hold:*

(i) *if $p \in C^{0, \frac{1}{|\log t|}}(\bar{\Omega}) \cap C_+(\bar{\Omega})$ and $t \in C(\bar{\Omega})$ is such that*

$$1 \leq t(x) \leq p^*(x) \quad \text{for all } x \in \bar{\Omega},$$

then the embedding

$$W^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^{t(\cdot)}(\Omega)$$

is continuous.

(ii) *if $t \in C_+(\bar{\Omega})$ is such that*

$$1 \leq t(x) < p^*(x) \quad \text{for all } x \in \bar{\Omega},$$

then the embedding

$$W^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^{t(\cdot)}(\Omega)$$

is compact.

Next, we introduce the nonlinear operator $F: W_0^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow \left(W_0^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega)\right)^*$ given by

$$\langle F(u), v \rangle := \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, dx, \quad (6)$$

for $u, v \in W_0^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ with $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ being the duality pairing between $W_0^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and its dual space $\left(W_0^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega)\right)^*$. Arguing as in the proof of Proposition 2.5 of Gasiński-Papageorgiou [11] or Rădulescu-Repovš [31, p.40], we have the following result which states the main properties of $F: W_0^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow \left(W_0^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega)\right)^*$.

Proposition 2.3. *The operator F defined by (6) is bounded, continuous, monotone (hence maximal monotone) and of type (S_+) , that is,*

$$u_n \xrightarrow{w} u \quad \text{in } W_0^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \quad \text{and} \quad \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle F(u_n), u_n - u \rangle \leq 0,$$

imply $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1, p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$.

Let E be a real Banach space with norm $\|\cdot\|_E$. A function $\varphi: E \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{R}} := \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ is said to be proper, convex and lower semicontinuous, if the following conditions are fulfilled:

- $D(\varphi) := \{u \in E : \varphi(u) < +\infty\} \neq \emptyset$;
- for any $u, v \in E$ and $t \in (0, 1)$, it holds $\varphi(tu + (1-t)v) \leq t\varphi(u) + (1-t)\varphi(v)$;
- $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(u_n) \geq \varphi(u)$ whenever the sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset E$ is such that $u_n \rightarrow u$ in E as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for some $u \in E$.

Let φ be a convex mapping. An element $x^* \in E^*$ is said to be a subgradient of φ at $u \in E$ if

$$\langle x^*, v - u \rangle \leq \varphi(v) - \varphi(u) \quad (7)$$

holds for all $v \in E$. The set of all elements $x^* \in E^*$ satisfying (7) is called the convex subdifferential of φ at u and is denoted by $\partial\varphi(u)$.

Besides, we recall the following definition, see, for example, Papageorgiou-Winkert [28, Definition 6.7.4].

Definition 2.4. Let (X, τ) be a Hausdorff topological space and let $\{A_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset 2^X$ be a sequence of sets. We define the τ -Kuratowski lower limit of the sets $\{A_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ by

$$\tau\text{-}\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} A_n := \left\{ x \in X \mid x = \tau\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n, x_n \in A_n \text{ for all } n \geq 1 \right\},$$

and the τ -Kuratowski upper limit of the sets $\{A_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ by

$$\tau\text{-}\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} A_n := \left\{ x \in X \mid x = \tau\text{-}\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} x_{n_k}, x_{n_k} \in A_{n_k}, n_1 < n_2 < \dots < n_k < \dots \right\}.$$

If

$$A = \tau\text{-}\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} A_n = \tau\text{-}\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} A_n,$$

then A is called τ -Kuratowski limit of the sets $\{A_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$.

In the end of this section, we recall the following surjectivity theorem for pseudomonotone operators with a maximal monotone operator perturbation. In fact, this theorem is a direct consequence of Le [15, Theorem 2.2] with the singular-valued case.

Theorem 2.5. *Let E be a real reflexive Banach space, let $R: D(R) \subset E \rightarrow 2^{E^*}$ be a maximal monotone operator, let $Q: E \rightarrow E^*$ be a bounded and pseudomonotone operator. Suppose that $l \in E^*$, and there are $x_0 \in E$ and $r \geq \|x_0\|_E$ satisfying $D(R) \cap B_r(0) \neq \emptyset$ and*

$$\langle Q(x) + \xi - l, x - x_0 \rangle_{E^* \times E} > 0$$

for all $x \in D(R)$ with $\|x\|_E = r$ and for all $\xi \in R(x)$. Then, the multi-valued mapping $Q + R: D(R) \rightarrow 2^{E^*}$ is surjective, so, there exists an element $x^* \in E$ such that $Q(x^*) + R(x^*) \ni l$.

3. Existence and compactness. The goal of this section is to prove the existence of a weak solution to problem (1) and the compactness of solution set of problem (1). Our main method is based on topological approaches, a surjectivity theory for pseudomonotone operators with a maximal monotone perturbation, and the theory of nonsmooth analysis.

Using the standard arguments, we give the definition of weak solution to problem (1) as follows.

Definition 3.1. Given $\lambda > 0$, $\theta \geq 0$ and $\Phi \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, we say that $u \in K(\Phi)$ is a weak solution of problem (1), if it fulfills the following inequality for all $v \in K(\Phi)$

$$\begin{aligned} & N(u) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla(v-u)) dx + M(u, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla(v-u)) dx \\ & - \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u, \nabla u)(v-u) dx \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $K(\Phi) := \left\{ u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \mid u(x) \leq \Phi(x) \text{ for a.e. } x \in \Omega \right\}$.

In what follows, we denote by $\mathcal{P}_\lambda(\theta, \Phi)$ the solution set in the sense of Definition 3.1 of problem (1) corresponding to $(\lambda, \theta) \in (0, +\infty) \times [0, +\infty)$ and $\Phi \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, namely,

$$\mathcal{P}_\lambda(\theta, \Phi) := \{u \in K(\Phi) \mid u \text{ is a solution of problem (1) corresponding to } (\lambda, \theta, \Phi)\}.$$

For the convenience of calculating and analyzing, in the sequel we always assume that Φ is nonnegative, i.e., $\Phi(x) \geq 0$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$.

For obtaining the existence of weak solutions to problem (1), we need to assume that the following hypotheses are satisfied:

H(pq): $p, q \in C_+(\overline{\Omega})$ with $q(x) < p(x)$ for all $x \in \overline{\Omega}$ and there exists $\xi_0 \in \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \{0\}$ such that for all $x \in \Omega$ the function $p_x: \Omega_x \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by $p_x(z) = p(x + z\xi_0)$ is monotone, where $\Omega_x := \{z \in \mathbb{R} : x + z\xi_0 \in \Omega\}$.

H(NM): $N: L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$ and $M: L^{p^*(\cdot)} \times [0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ satisfy the following properties:

(i) N is bounded and continuous in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ such that $\inf_{u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)} N(u) \geq a_N > 0$, where p^* is the critical exponent of p in the domain Ω given in (4);

(ii) M is bounded and continuous in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \times [0, +\infty)$.

H(f): $f: \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a Carathéodory function (i.e., $f(\cdot, s, \xi): \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is measurable in Ω for all $(s, \xi) \in \mathbb{R}^{N+1}$ and $f(x, \cdot, \cdot): \mathbb{R}^{N+1} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous for a.e. $x \in \Omega$) and reads the following conditions:

(i) there exist a function $a_f \in L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ with $1 \leq r(x) < p^*(x)$ for all $x \in \overline{\Omega}$, and two constants $b_f, c_f \geq 0$ such that the following inequality holds

$$|f(x, s, \xi)| \leq a_f(x) + b_f |s|^{r(x)-1} + c_f |\xi|^{\frac{p(x)r(x)}{r(x)-1}}$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$ and all $(s, \xi) \in \mathbb{R}^{N+1}$;

(ii) there are two constants $\alpha_f, \beta_f \geq 0$ and a function $d_f \in L^1(\Omega)$ with $d_f(x) \geq 0$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$ satisfying

$$f(x, s, \xi)s \leq d_f(x) + \alpha_f |s|^{p(x)} + \beta_f |\xi|^{p(x)}$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$ and all $(s, \xi) \in \mathbb{R}^{N+1}$.

Remark 3.2. It is not difficult to prove that

- the following functions satisfy hypothesis H(NM)(i):

$$N(u) := e^{\|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)}},$$

$$N(u) := a_N + \|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)},$$

$$N(u) := a_N + \ln \left(1 + \|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)} \right),$$

for all $u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, for some $a_N > 0$.

- the following functions satisfy hypothesis H(NM)(ii):

$$M(u, \theta) := \sqrt{1 + \theta} \|u\|_{W_0^{1,q(\cdot)}(\Omega)},$$

$$M(u, \theta) := \theta \|u\|_{W_0^{1,q(\cdot)}(\Omega)},$$

$$M(u, \theta) := \ln \left(1 + \theta + \|u\|_{W_0^{1,q(\cdot)}(\Omega)} \right),$$

for all $u \in W_0^{1,q(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and $\theta \geq 0$.

Fixed $\theta \in [0, +\infty)$, let us introduce the nonlinear function $\mathcal{Q}: W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow (W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega))^*$ given by

$$\langle \mathcal{Q}(u), v \rangle := N(u) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla v) dx + M(u, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla v) dx \quad (9)$$

for all $u, v \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. The following lemma points out that \mathcal{Q} is well-defined, bounded, continuous and has (S_+) -property.

Lemma 3.3. *Suppose that hypotheses $H(pq)$ and $H(NM)$ hold. Then, the operator $\mathcal{Q}: W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow (W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega))^*$ defined in (9) is well-defined, bounded, continuous and has (S_+) -property.*

Proof. For any $u, v \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, it follows from Young inequality that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{N(u)}{\|\nabla v\|_{p(\cdot)} \max\{\|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_- - 1}, \|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_+ - 1}\}} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla v) dx \right| \\ & \leq N(u) \int_{\Omega} \frac{|\nabla u|^{p(x)-1}}{\max\{\|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_- - 1}, \|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_+ - 1}\}} \cdot \frac{|\nabla v|}{\|\nabla v\|_{p(\cdot)}} dx \\ & \leq N(u) \int_{\Omega} \frac{|\nabla u|^{p(x)-1}}{\|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p(x)-1}} \cdot \frac{|\nabla v|}{\|\nabla v\|_{p(\cdot)}} dx \\ & \leq N(u) \int_{\Omega} \frac{|\nabla u|^{p(x)}}{p'(x) \|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p(x)}} dx + N(u) \int_{\Omega} \frac{|\nabla v|^{p(x)}}{p(x) \|\nabla v\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p(x)}} dx \\ & \leq \frac{N(u)}{p'_-} \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{|\nabla u|}{\|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}} \right)^{p(x)} dx + \frac{N(u)}{p_-} \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{|\nabla v|}{\|\nabla v\|_{p(\cdot)}} \right)^{p(x)} dx \\ & = \frac{N(u)}{p'_-} \varrho_{p(\cdot)} \left(\frac{|\nabla u|}{\|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}} \right) + \frac{N(u)}{p_-} \varrho_{p(\cdot)} \left(\frac{|\nabla v|}{\|\nabla v\|_{p(\cdot)}} \right) \\ & = \frac{N(u)}{p'_-} + \frac{N(u)}{p_-}, \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the inequality $\max\{\|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_- - 1}, \|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_+ - 1}\} \geq \|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p(x)-1}$ for all $x \in \bar{\Omega}$ and the last equality is obtained by Proposition 2.1(i). Hence, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| N(u) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla v) dx \right| \\ & \leq \left[\frac{N(u)}{p'_-} + \frac{N(u)}{p_-} \right] \|\nabla v\|_{p(\cdot)} \max\{\|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_- - 1}, \|\nabla u\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_+ - 1}\}. \end{aligned}$$

A similar inequality can be derived for the second term in the right hand side of (9), using a suitable embedding constant c_q too. Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{Q}(u)\|_{(W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega))^*} & = \sup_{v \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega), \|v\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)} = 1} \langle \mathcal{Q}(u), v \rangle \\ & \leq \left[\frac{N(u)}{p'_-} + \frac{N(u)}{p_-} \right] \max \left\{ \|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)}^{p_- - 1}, \|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)}^{p_+ - 1} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$+ c_q \left[\frac{M(u, \theta)}{q'_-} + \frac{M(u, \theta)}{q_-} \right] \max \left\{ \|u\|_{W_0^{1,q(\cdot)}(\Omega)}^{q_- - 1}, \|u\|_{W_0^{1,q(\cdot)}(\Omega)}^{q_+ - 1} \right\},$$

for some $c_q > 0$. This means that \mathcal{Q} is well-defined and bounded.

Let $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ be a convergent sequence, i.e., there exists $u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ such that $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Without loss of generality, we may assume that $\nabla u_n(x) \rightarrow \nabla u(x)$ in \mathbb{R}^N for a.e. $x \in \Omega$. Then, for each $v \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n \, dx - N(u) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u, \nabla v \, dx \right| \\ & \leq N(u) \left| \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n - |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u, \nabla v \right) \, dx \right| \\ & \quad + |N(u_n) - N(u)| \left| \int_{\Omega} \left(\nabla u_n |^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n, \nabla v \right) \, dx \right| \\ & \leq N(u) \left| \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n - |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u, \nabla v \right) \, dx \right| \\ & \quad + |N(u_n) - N(u)| \left[\frac{1}{p'_-} + \frac{1}{p_-} \right] \|\nabla v\|_{p(\cdot)} \max\{\|\nabla u_n\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_- - 1}, \|\nabla u_n\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_+ - 1}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Passing to the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for the estimates above and utilizing Lebesgue dominated convergence theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n \, dx - N(u) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u, \nabla v \, dx \right| \\ & \leq N(u) \int_{\Omega} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n - |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u \right| |\nabla v| \, dx \\ & \quad + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |N(u_n) - N(u)| \left[\frac{1}{p'_-} + \frac{1}{p_-} \right] \|\nabla v\|_{p(\cdot)} \max\{\|\nabla u_n\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_- - 1}, \|\nabla u_n\|_{p(\cdot)}^{p_+ - 1}\}, \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the continuity of N and the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} & N(u) \left| \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n - |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u, \nabla v \right) \, dx \right| \\ & \leq \left[\frac{N(u)}{p'_-} + \frac{N(u)}{p_-} \right] \|v\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)} \left(\max \left\{ \|u_n\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)}^{p_- - 1}, \|u_n\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)}^{p_+ - 1} \right\} \right) \\ & \quad + \max \left\{ \|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)}^{p_- - 1}, \|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)}^{p_+ - 1} \right\} \\ & < +\infty. \end{aligned}$$

Under the analysis above, we deduce that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathcal{Q}u_n - \mathcal{Q}u\|_{(W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega))^*} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{v \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega), \|v\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)} = 1} \langle \mathcal{Q}u_n - \mathcal{Q}u, v \rangle = 0.$$

This means that \mathcal{Q} is continuous.

Finally, we show that \mathcal{Q} has (S_+) -property. Let $\{u_n\} \subset W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and $u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ be such that

$$u_n \xrightarrow{w} u \text{ in } W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \text{ and } \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathcal{Q}u_n, u_n - u \rangle \leq 0.$$

Hence, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \langle \mathcal{Q}u_n, u_n - u \rangle \\
 &= N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx \\
 & \quad + M(u_n, \theta) \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} \nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx \\
 & \geq N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx \\
 & \quad + M(u_n, \theta) \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u|^{q(x)-2} \nabla u, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx,
 \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality is obtained by using the monotonicity of $q(\cdot)$ -Laplace operator. From the boundedness of M and the convergence $u_n \xrightarrow{w} u$, we deduce that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(u_n, \theta) \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u|^{q(x)-2} \nabla u, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx = 0.$$

Therefore, it yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 & \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathcal{Q}u_n, u_n - u \rangle \\
 & \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx \\
 & \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_N}{2} \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx \\
 & \quad + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(N(u_n) - \frac{a_N}{2} \right) \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx \\
 & \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_N}{2} \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx \\
 & \quad + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(N(u_n) - \frac{a_N}{2} \right) \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx \\
 & = \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_N}{2} \int_{\Omega} \left(|\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} \nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u) \right) dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

We are now in a position to invoke Proposition 2.3 for obtaining that $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Consequently, we conclude that \mathcal{Q} has (S_+) -property. \square

Let us consider the Nemytskii operator $\mathcal{N}_f: W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \subset L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow L^{r'(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ of f defined by

$$\mathcal{N}_f(u)(x) := f(x, u(x), \nabla u(x)) \text{ for a.e. } x \in \Omega \text{ and all } u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega). \quad (10)$$

The following lemma points out that \mathcal{N}_f is well-defined, bounded and continuous.

Lemma 3.4. *Assume that hypotheses $H(f)$ are fulfilled. Then $\mathcal{N}_f: W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \subset L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow L^{r'(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ is well-defined, bounded and continuous.*

Proof. Let $u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ be arbitrary. From hypotheses $H(f)$, one has

$$\int_{\Omega} |f(x, u(x), \nabla u)|^{r'(x)} dx \leq \int_{\Omega} \left(a_f(x) + b_f |u|^{r(x)-1} + c_f |\nabla u|^{\frac{p(x)}{r(x)'}} \right)^{r'(x)} dx$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq c_0 \int_{\Omega} \left(a_f(x)^{r'(x)} + b_f |u|^{r(x)} + c_f |\nabla u|^{p(x)} \right) dx \\
&= c_0 \left(\varrho_{r'(\cdot)}(a_f) + b_f \varrho_{r(\cdot)}(u) + c_f \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) \right) \quad (11)
\end{aligned}$$

for some $c_0 > 0$. Therefore, we can observe that $\mathcal{N}_f: W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \subset L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow L^{r'(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ is well-defined and bounded. Moreover, it follows from Lebesgue dominated convergence theorem that \mathcal{N}_f is continuous. \square

We are now in a position to state the existence theorem for problem (1) as follows.

Theorem 3.5. *Assume that hypotheses $H(pq)$, $H(MN)$ and $H(f)$ are satisfied. Then, for each $\theta \geq 0$ fixed, there exists a constant $\lambda^* > 0$ such that the solution set $\mathcal{P}_\lambda(\theta, \Phi)$ of problem (1) is nonempty and compact for all $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*)$.*

Proof. Existence. Let us consider the embedding operator $\gamma: W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ with its dual operator $\gamma^*: L^{r'(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow \left(W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)\right)^*$. Keeping in mind that $1 < r(x) < p^*(x)$ for all $x \in \bar{\Omega}$, hence from Proposition 2.2(ii), we can observe that the operators γ and γ^* are both compact. Using the standard arguments, it is not difficult to see that $u \in K(\Phi)$ is a solution of problem (1) if and only if it solves the following nonlinear inclusion problem

$$\mathcal{Q}(u) - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f(u) + \partial I_{K(\Phi)}(u) \ni 0 \text{ in } \left(W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)\right)^*, \quad (12)$$

where $\partial I_{K(\Phi)}$ is the subdifferential of the indicator function

$$I_{K(\Phi)}(u) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } u \in K(\Phi), \\ +\infty & \text{if } u \notin K(\Phi). \end{cases}$$

We have the following properties.

Property I. $\mathcal{Q} - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f: W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \subset L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow \left(W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)\right)^*$ is bounded and pseudomonotone.

The boundedness of $\mathcal{Q} - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f$ is a direct consequence of Lemmas 3.3 and 3.4. Let $\{u_n\} \subset W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ satisfy $u_n \xrightarrow{w} u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathcal{Q}(u_n) - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f(u_n), u_n - u \rangle \leq 0$. The compactness of γ and boundedness of \mathcal{N}_f imply

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f(u_n), u_n - u \rangle = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathcal{N}_f(u_n), \gamma(u_n - u) \rangle_{L^{r'(\cdot)}(\Omega) \times L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega)} = 0.$$

Therefore, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &\geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathcal{Q}(u_n), u_n - u \rangle - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f(u_n), u_n - u \rangle \\
&= \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathcal{Q}(u_n), u_n - u \rangle.
\end{aligned}$$

Applying Lemma 3.3, it yields $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Whereas, it follows from the continuity of \mathcal{Q} and \mathcal{N}_f that $\mathcal{Q}(u_n) - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f(u_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}(u) - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f(u)$ in $\left(W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)\right)^*$. This indicates that $\mathcal{Q} - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f: W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \subset L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow \left(W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)\right)^*$ is pseudomonotone too.

Property II. *There exists $\lambda^* > 0$ such that for all $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*)$, the mapping $\mathcal{Q} - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f: W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \subset L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow \left(W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)\right)^*$ is coercive.*

For any $u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \langle \mathcal{Q}(u) - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f(u), u \rangle \\
 &= N(u) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)} dx + M(u, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{q(x)} dx - \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u(x), \nabla u(x)) u(x) dx \\
 &\geq N(u) \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) + M(u, \theta) \varrho_{q(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) - \int_{\Omega} \lambda \left(d_f(x) + \alpha_f |u|^{p(x)} + \beta_f |\nabla u|^{p(x)} \right) dx \\
 &\geq N(u) \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) + M(u, \theta) \varrho_{q(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) \\
 &\quad - \lambda \left(\|d_f\|_1 + \alpha_f \hat{\lambda}^{-1} \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) + \beta_f \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) \right) \\
 &\geq \left(a_N - \lambda(\alpha_f \hat{\lambda}^{-1} + \beta_f) \right) \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) - \lambda \|d_f\|_1,
 \end{aligned}$$

with $\hat{\lambda} := \inf_{u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \setminus \{0\}} \frac{\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)} dx}{\int_{\Omega} |u|^{p(x)} dx} > 0$ being the Rayleigh quotient (where the positivity is a consequence of hypothesis H(pq), see also [34, Remark 2.8]), hence we have

$$\hat{\lambda} \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(u) \leq \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega).$$

It is not hard to see that if we take $\lambda^* = \frac{a_N}{\alpha_f \hat{\lambda}^{-1} + \beta_f}$, then for each $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*)$ the mapping $\mathcal{Q} - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f : W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \subset L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow \left(W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \right)^*$ is coercive, by applying Proposition 2.1(vi).

Recall that $K(\Phi)$ is nonempty, closed and convex, so, $I_{K(\Phi)}$ is proper, convex and l.s.c., and $\partial I_{K(\Phi)}$ is maximal monotone. It follows from Property II that for any $u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and $\zeta \in \partial I_{K(\Phi)}(u)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \langle \mathcal{Q}(u) - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f(u) + \zeta, u \rangle \\
 &\geq \left(a_N - \lambda(\alpha_f \hat{\lambda}^{-1} + \beta_f) \right) \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) - \lambda \|d_f\|_1 + I_{K(\Phi)}(u) - I_{K(\Phi)}(0) \\
 &\geq \left(a_N - \lambda(\alpha_f \hat{\lambda}^{-1} + \beta_f) \right) \max \left\{ \|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)}^{p^+}, \|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)}^{p^-} \right\} \\
 &\quad - \lambda \|d_f\|_1 - a_K \|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)} - b_K,
 \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the fact that $0 \in K(\Phi)$, Proposition 2.1 and [3, Proposition 1.10], and $a_K, b_K \geq 0$ are such that $I_{K(\Phi)}(u) \geq -a_K \|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)} - b_K$ for all $u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Therefore, we can find a constant $\delta > 0$ such that

$$\langle \mathcal{Q}(u) - \lambda \gamma^* \mathcal{N}_f(u) + \zeta, u \rangle > 0$$

for all $u \in K(\Phi)$ with $\|u\|_{W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)} = \delta$ and for all $\zeta \in \partial I_{K(\Phi)}(u)$. To conclude, we can see that all conditions of Theorem 2.5 are verified. Employing this theorem, there exists a function $u \in K(\Phi)$ to solve inclusion (12). For any $v \in K(\Phi)$, multiplying (12) by $v - u$ we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & N(u) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla(v-u)) dx + M(u, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla(v-u)) dx \\
 &\quad - \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u, \nabla u)(v-u) dx \geq 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

This indicates that $u \in K(\Phi)$ is a weak solution of (1).

Compactness. Let $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset K(\Phi)$ be a solution sequence of problem (1). Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(v - u_n)) dx \\ & + M(u_n, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(v - u_n)) dx \\ & - \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n)(v - u_n) dx \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

for all $v \in K(\Phi)$ and all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Putting $v = 0 \in K(\Phi)$ into the inequality, one has

$$\left(a_N - \lambda(\alpha_f \hat{\lambda}^{-1} + \beta_f) \right) \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u_n|) - \lambda \|d_f\|_1 \leq 0.$$

This reveals that $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ is bounded. Passing to a subsequence if necessary, we may assume that $u_n \xrightarrow{w} u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ for some $u \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. The convexity and closedness of $K(\Phi)$ guarantees that $u \in K(\Phi)$. Letting $v = u$ into (13) and passing to the upper limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx \right. \\ & \left. + M(u_n, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx \right) \\ & \leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n)(u_n - u) dx. \end{aligned}$$

The latter together with the compactness of the embedding $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ into $L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and hypotheses $H(f)$ implies

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathcal{Q}u_n, u_n - u \rangle \leq 0.$$

But, the (S_+) -property of \mathcal{Q} (see Lemma 3.3) points out that $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for inequality (13) and using the continuity of N, M and f , it yields that u is a weak solution of problem (1). Consequently, solution sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset K(\Phi)$ has a subsequence which converges strongly to a solution of problem (1), namely, the solution set of problem (1) is compact. \square

When p, q are constants, we have the following corollary.

Corollary 3.6. *Assume that $1 < q < p$ and $H(NM)$ and $H(f)$ are satisfied. Then, for each $\theta > 0$, there exists $\lambda^* > 0$ such that the solution set of problem (2) is nonempty and compact in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$.*

If $\Phi \equiv +\infty$, then we have the following result.

Corollary 3.7. *Assume that $H(NM)$, $H(pq)$ and $H(f)$ are satisfied. Then, for each $\theta > 0$, there exists $\lambda^* > 0$ such that the solution set of problem (3) is nonempty and compact in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$.*

4. Asymptotic behavior and stability. In this section, we will move our attention to establish some results concerning asymptotic behavior and stability of solution set for problem (1) when the $q(\cdot)$ -Laplace operator and nonlinear convection term are modulated by parameters, and the obstacle function is perturbed by a convergent sequence.

Let us consider the sets $\Lambda := (0, \lambda^*)$ and $\Upsilon_\lambda := \cup_{\theta \geq 0} \mathcal{P}_\lambda(\theta, \Phi)$, where λ^* is given in Theorem 3.5. The following lemma reveals that Υ_λ is uniformly bounded in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$.

Lemma 4.1. *Suppose that the conditions of Theorem 3.5 are fulfilled. Then, for each $\lambda \in \Lambda$ the set Υ_λ is uniformly bounded in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Moreover, we have:*

- (i) *if $\Theta \subset [0, +\infty)$ is a bounded set, then the set $\cup_{\theta \in \Theta} \mathcal{P}_\lambda(\theta, \Phi)$ is relatively compact in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$.*
- (ii) *if $\Theta \subset [0, +\infty)$ is compact, then the set $\cup_{\theta \in \Theta} \mathcal{P}_\lambda(\theta)$ is compact.*

Proof. From Theorem 3.5, we can see that for each $\lambda \in \Lambda$ the set Υ_λ is nonempty. Let $u \in \Upsilon_\lambda$ be arbitrary. Then, there exists $\theta \geq 0$ such that $u \in \mathcal{P}_\lambda(\theta, \Phi)$. Inserting $v = 0 \in K(\Phi)$ into (8), it is not difficult to obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} a_N \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|) &= a_N \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)} dx \\ &\leq N(u) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)} dx + M(u, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{q(x)} dx \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u, \nabla u) u dx \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega} \lambda (d_f(x) + \alpha_f |u|^{p(x)} + \beta_f |\nabla u|^{p(x)}) dx \\ &= \lambda (\|d_f\|_{1,\Omega} + \alpha_f \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(u) + \beta_f \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(|\nabla u|)). \end{aligned}$$

Because of $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*)$, we can see that Υ_λ is bounded in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$.

(i) Assume that $\Theta \subset [0, +\infty)$ is a bounded set. Let $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \cup_{\theta \in \Theta} \mathcal{P}_\lambda(\theta, \Phi)$ be a solution sequence. So, there is a sequence $\{\theta_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \Theta$ such that $u_n \in \mathcal{P}_\lambda(\theta_n, \Phi)$, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} &N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(v - u_n)) dx \\ &+ M(u_n, \theta_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(v - u_n)) dx \\ &- \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n) (v - u_n) dx \geq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

for all $v \in K(\Phi)$. But, the boundedness of $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ and Θ allows to find a subsequence, still denoted by the same way, such that $\theta_n \rightarrow \theta$ in \mathbb{R} for some $\theta \in [0, +\infty)$ and $u_n \xrightarrow{w} u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ with $u \in K(\Phi)$. Putting $v = u$ into (14) and letting the upper limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, it yields

$$\begin{aligned} &\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n) (u_n - u) dx \\ &\geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx \\ &\quad + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(u_n, \theta_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx \\ &\geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx \\ &\quad + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(u_n, \theta_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx. \end{aligned}$$

Whereas, the boundedness of M and compactness of embedding of $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ into $L^{r(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ imply that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n)(u_n - u) dx \\ &\geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx \\ &\quad + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(u_n, \theta_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx \\ &\geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathcal{Q}(u_n), u_n - u \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Utilizing Lemma 3.3, we infer $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for inequality (14) and employing the continuity of N , M and f , it gives that $u \in K(\Phi)$ is a solution of problem (1) associated to (λ, θ, Φ) . Therefore, we have $u \in \cup_{\theta \in \Theta} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi)$.

(ii) Let Θ be compact and let $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \cup_{\theta \in \Theta} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi)$ be a solution sequence. It follows from the proof of statement (i) that $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is relatively compact and there exists a sequence $\{\theta_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \Theta$ satisfying $u_n \in \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta_n, \Phi)$. The compactness of Θ and $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ turns out that, passing to a subsequence if necessary, there are $\theta \in \Theta$ and $u \in K(\Phi)$ such that $\theta_n \rightarrow \theta$ and $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ for inequality (14), we infer that u is a solution of problem (1) corresponding to $(\lambda, \theta) \in \Lambda \times \Theta$ and Φ . This means that $u \in \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi)$, i.e., $\cup_{\theta \in \Theta} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi)$ is compact. \square

Theorem 4.2. *Under the assumptions of Theorem 3.5, if sequences $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \Lambda$ and $\{\theta_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset [0, +\infty)$ are such that*

$$\lambda_n \rightarrow \lambda \text{ and } \theta_n \rightarrow \theta \quad (15)$$

for some $\lambda \in \Lambda$ and $\theta \geq 0$, then we have

$$w - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi) = s - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi) \subset \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi).$$

Proof. Let $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \Lambda$ and $\{\theta_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset [0, +\infty)$ be such that (15) holds. Theorem 3.5 and Lemma 3.3 ensure that $w - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi)$ is nonempty. If $u \in w - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi)$, then, without loss of generality, we may assume that there is a sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ with $u_n \in \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi)$ such that $u_n \xrightarrow{w} u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} &N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(v - u_n)) dx \\ &+ M(u_n, \theta_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(v - u_n)) dx \\ &- \int_{\Omega} \lambda_n f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n)(v - u_n) dx \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

for all $v \in K(\Phi)$. Arguing as in the proof of Lemma 4.1, we have $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. This reveals that $w - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi) = s - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi)$. Passing to the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for (16), it is not hard to see that $u \in K(\Phi)$ is a solution of problem (1) corresponding to (λ, θ, Φ) , thus, $u \in \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi)$. Consequently, we conclude that $w - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi) = s - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi) \subset \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi)$. \square

Furthermore, we have the following proposition.

Proposition 4.3. *Assume that all conditions of Theorem 3.5 are satisfied, and for any bounded set $B \subset W_0^{1,q(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and $\{\theta_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset [0, +\infty)$ with $\theta_n \rightarrow +\infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ it holds $M(u, \theta_n) \rightarrow +\infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, uniformly for $u \in B$. If sequences $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \Lambda$ and $\{\theta_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset [0, +\infty)$ are such that $\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \lambda_n < \lambda^*$ and $\theta_n \rightarrow +\infty$, then we have*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi) = \{0\}.$$

Proof. Applying the same arguments as in the proof of Lemma 4.1, we can see that $\cup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi)$ is uniformly bounded in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Let $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset K(\Phi)$ be such that $u_n \in \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi)$, that is,

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{N(u_n)}{M(u_n, \theta_n)} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(v - u_n)) dx \\ & + \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(v - u_n)) dx \\ & - \frac{\lambda_n}{M(u_n, \theta_n)} \int_{\Omega} f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n)(v - u_n) dx \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

for all $v \in K(\Phi)$. Passing to a subsequence if necessary, we may suppose that $u_n \xrightarrow{w} u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Arguing as in the proof of Lemma 4.1, we have $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ owing to $M(u_n, \theta_n) \rightarrow +\infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Passing to the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for inequality (17), we can see that

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla(v - u)) dx \geq 0$$

for all $v \in K(\Phi)$. Because of $v = 0 \in K(\Phi)$, hence we have

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{q(x)} dx \leq 0.$$

This means that $\nabla u = 0$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, namely, $u = 0$. Consequently, we conclude that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi) = \{0\}$. \square

In the end of this section, we give a stability result to solution set of problem (1), when the obstacle function is perturbed by an approximating sequence.

Theorem 4.4. *Under the assumptions of Theorem 3.5, if $\{\Phi_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and $\Phi \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ are such that $\Phi_n \geq 0$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$ and $\Phi_n \rightarrow \Phi$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, then, for each $\lambda \in \Lambda$ and $\theta \in [0, +\infty)$ fixed, we have*

$$w - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi_n) = s - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi_n) \subset \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi).$$

Proof. Arguing as in the proof of Lemma 4.1, it is not difficult to see that the solution set $\cup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi_n)$ is bounded. Hence, $w - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi_n) \neq \emptyset$. Let $u \in w - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi_n)$ be arbitrary. Without loss of generality, we may assume that there exists a sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ such that $u_n \in \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi_n)$ and $u_n \xrightarrow{w} u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. Indeed, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(v - u_n)) dx \\ & + M(u_n, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(v - u_n)) dx \end{aligned}$$

$$- \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n)(v - u_n) dx \geq 0 \quad (18)$$

for all $v \in K(\Phi_n)$. Recall that $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ embeds in $L^1(\Omega)$ compactly and $\Phi_n \rightarrow \Phi$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, hence we may assume that $u_n(x) \rightarrow u(x)$ and $\Phi_n(x) \rightarrow \Phi(x)$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$. Therefore, we have $u(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n(x) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Phi_n(x) = \Phi(x)$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, i.e., $u \in K(\Phi)$.

For any $z \in K(\Phi)$, we set $w_n = z - (\Phi - \Phi_n)^+$. Because of $\Phi_n \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, it is not difficult to see that $w_n \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and $w_n(x) \leq \Phi_n(x)$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, that is, $w_n \in K(\Phi_n)$. Inserting $v = u - (\Phi - \Phi_n)^+$ into (18), it yields

$$\begin{aligned} & N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx \\ & + M(u_n, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx \\ & \leq \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n)(u - u_n - (\Phi - \Phi_n)^+) dx \\ & \quad - N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(\Phi - \Phi_n)^+) dx \\ & \quad - M(u_n, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(\Phi - \Phi_n)^+) dx. \end{aligned}$$

Taking the upper limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for the inequality above, it yields

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(u_n - u)) dx \leq 0.$$

So, from Lemma 3.3, we have $u_n \rightarrow u$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$. This reveals that

$$s - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi_n) = s - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi) \neq \emptyset.$$

Moreover, we take $v = w_n$ with $w_n = z - (\Phi - \Phi_n)^+$ for $z \in K(\Phi)$ into (18) to get

$$\begin{aligned} & N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(w_n - u_n)) dx \\ & + M(u_n, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(w_n - u_n)) dx \\ & - \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n)(w_n - u_n) dx \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Passing to the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and using the convergences $w_n \rightarrow u$ and $\Phi_n \rightarrow \Phi$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} & N(u) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla(z - u)) dx + M(u, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u, \nabla(z - u)) dx \\ & - \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u, \nabla u)(z - u) dx \\ & = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} N(u_n) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{p(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla(w_n - u_n)) dx \\ & \quad - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \lambda f(x, u_n, \nabla u_n)(w_n - u_n) dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(u_n, \theta) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n|^{q(x)-2} (\nabla u_n, \nabla (w_n - u_n)) dx \\
& \geq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

The arbitrariness of $z \in K(\Phi)$ indicates that u is a solution of problem (1) corresponding to (λ, θ, Φ) . Therefore, we have $w - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi_n) = s - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi_n) \subset \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi)$. \square

Applying the same arguments as in the proof of Theorem 4.4, we have the following proposition.

Proposition 4.5. *Under the assumptions of Theorem 3.5, if $\{\Phi_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, $\Phi \in W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and sequences $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \Lambda$ and $\{\theta_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset [0, +\infty)$ are such that $\Phi_n \geq 0$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, $\Phi_n \rightarrow \Phi$ in $W_0^{1,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and $\lambda_n \rightarrow \lambda$ and $\theta_n \rightarrow \theta$ with $\lambda \in \Lambda$ and $\theta < +\infty$, then, it holds*

$$w - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi_n) = s - \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{P}_{\lambda_n}(\theta_n, \Phi_n) \subset \mathcal{P}_{\lambda}(\theta, \Phi).$$

Data availability statement. Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Acknowledgments. This project has received funding from the Natural Science Foundation of Guangxi Grant Nos. 2021GXNSFFA196004 and 2022AC21071, NNSF of China Grant No. 12001478, the China Postdoctoral Science Foundation funded project No. 2022M721560, the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 823731 CONMECH, and National Science Center of Poland under Preludium Project No. 2017/25/N/ST1/00611. The third author is supported by the research fund of University of Palermo: “FFR 2023 Calogero Vetro”.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. S. Albalawi, N. H. Alharthi and F. Vetro, Gradient and parameter dependent Dirichlet $(p(x), q(x))$ -Laplace type problem, *Mathematics*, **10** (2022), 1336.
- [2] A. Bahrouni, V. D. Rădulescu and D. Repovš, Double phase transonic flow problems with variable growth: Nonlinear patterns and stationary waves, *Nonlinearity*, **32** (2019), 2481-2495.
- [3] H. Brézis, *Functional Analysis, Sobolev Spaces and Partial Differential Equations*, Springer, New York, 2011.
- [4] S.-S. Byun and E. Ko, Global $C^{1,\alpha}$ regularity and existence of multiple solutions for singular $p(x)$ -Laplacian equations, *Calc. Var. Partial Differential Equations*, **56** (2017), Paper No. 76, 29 pp.
- [5] S. Carl, V. K. Le and P. Winkert, Multi-valued variational inequalities for variable exponent double phase problems: Comparison and extremality results, preprint 2022, [arXiv:2201.02801](https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.02801).
- [6] L. Diening, P. Harjulehto, P. Hästö and M. Růžička, *Lebesgue and Sobolev Spaces with Variable Exponents*, Springer, Heidelberg, 2011.
- [7] X. Fan, Boundary trace embedding theorems for variable exponent Sobolev spaces, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, **339** (2008), 1395-1412.
- [8] F. Faraci, D. Motreanu and D. Puglisi, Positive solutions of quasi-linear elliptic equations with dependence on the gradient, *Calc. Var. Partial Differential Equations*, **54** (2015), 525-538.
- [9] F. Faraci and D. Puglisi, A singular semilinear problem with dependence on the gradient, *J. Differential Equations*, **260** (2016), 3327-3349.
- [10] G. M. Figueiredo and G. F. Madeira, Positive maximal and minimal solutions for non-homogeneous elliptic equations depending on the gradient, *J. Differential Equations*, **274** (2021), 857-875.

- [11] L. Gasiński and N. S. Papageorgiou, [Anisotropic nonlinear Neumann problems](#), *Calc. Var. Partial Differential Equations*, **42** (2011), 323-354.
- [12] L. Gasiński and N. S. Papageorgiou, [Positive solutions for nonlinear elliptic problems with dependence on the gradient](#), *J. Differential Equations*, **263** (2017), 1451-1476.
- [13] L. Gasiński and P. Winkert, [Existence and uniqueness results for double phase problems with convection term](#), *J. Differential Equations*, **268** (2020), 4183-4193.
- [14] A. Iannizzotto and N. S. Papageorgiou, [Existence of three nontrivial solutions for nonlinear Neumann hemivariational inequalities](#), *Nonlinear Anal.*, **70** (2009), 3285-3297.
- [15] V. K. Le, [A range and existence theorem for pseudomonotone perturbations of maximal monotone operators](#), *Proc. Am. Math. Soc.*, **139** (2011), 1645-1658.
- [16] Y. Liu, Z. Liu, C.-F. Wen, J.-C. Yao and S. Zeng, [Existence of solutions for a class of noncoercive variational-hemivariational inequalities arising in contact problems](#), *Appl. Math. Optim.*, **84** (2021), 2037-2059.
- [17] Y. Liu, S. Migórski, V. T. Nguyen and S. Zeng, [Existence and convergence results for an elastic frictional contact problem with nonmonotone subdifferential boundary conditions](#), *Acta Math. Sci.*, **41** (2021), 1151-1168.
- [18] Z. Liu, D. Motreanu and S. Zeng, [Positive solutions for nonlinear singular elliptic equations of \$p\$ -Laplacian type with dependence on the gradient](#), *Calc. Var. Partial Differential Equations*, **58** (2019), Paper No. 28, 22 pp.
- [19] Z. Liu and N. S. Papageorgiou, [Double phase Dirichlet problems with unilateral constraints](#), *J. Differential Equations*, **316** (2022), 249-269.
- [20] Z. Liu, S. Zeng, L. Gasiński and Y.-H. Kim, [Nonlocal double phase complementarity systems with convection term and mixed boundary conditions](#), *J. Geometric Anal.*, **32** (2022), Paper No. 241, 33 pp.
- [21] S. A. Marano and P. Winkert, [On a quasilinear elliptic problem with convection term and nonlinear boundary condition](#), *Nonlinear Anal.*, **187** (2019), 159-169.
- [22] S. Migórski, A. A. Khan and S. Zeng, [Inverse problems for nonlinear quasi-hemivariational inequalities with application to mixed boundary value problems](#), *Inverse Problems*, **36** (2020), 024006, 20 pp.
- [23] S. Migórski, A. A. Khan and S. Zeng, [Inverse problems for nonlinear quasi-variational inequalities with an application to implicit obstacle problems of \$p\$ -Laplacian type](#), *Inverse Problems*, **35** (2019), 035004, 14 pp.
- [24] G. Mingione and V. Rădulescu, [Recent developments in problems with nonstandard growth and nonuniform ellipticity](#), *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, **501** (2021), 125197, 41 pp.
- [25] N. S. Papageorgiou, V. D. Rădulescu and D. D. Repovš, [Positive solutions for nonlinear Neumann problems with singular terms and convection](#), *J. Math. Pures Appl.*, **136** (2020), 1-21.
- [26] N. S. Papageorgiou, V. D. Rădulescu and D. D. Repovš, [Anisotropic \$\(p, q\)\$ -equations with gradient dependent reaction](#), *Nonlinearity*, **34** (2021), 5319-5343.
- [27] N. S. Papageorgiou, V. D. Rădulescu and Y. Zhang, [Anisotropic singular double phase Dirichlet problems](#), *Discrete Cont. Dyn. Syst.-S*, **14** (2021), 4465-4502.
- [28] N. S. Papageorgiou and P. Winkert, *Applied Nonlinear Functional Analysis. An Introduction*, De Gruyter, Berlin, 2018.
- [29] N. S. Papageorgiou and P. Winkert, [Positive solutions for singular anisotropic \$\(p, q\)\$ -equations](#), *J. Geometric Anal.*, **31** (2021), 11849-11877.
- [30] V. D. Rădulescu, [Isotropic and anisotropic double-phase problems: Old and new](#), *Opuscula Math.*, **39** (2019), 259-279.
- [31] V. D. Rădulescu and D. D. Repovš, *Partial Differential Equations with Variable Exponents*, CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 2015.
- [32] A. Salmani, [Existence and uniqueness result for nonlinear anisotropic elliptic unilateral problems with variable exponent and measure data](#), *Rend. Circ. Mat. Palermo, II. Ser.*, **72** (2023), 1687-1717.
- [33] K. Saoudi and A. Ghanmi, [A multiplicity result for a singular equation involving the \$p\(x\)\$ -Laplace operator](#), *Complex Var. Elliptic Equ.*, **62** (2017), 695-725.
- [34] F. Vetro and P. Winkert, [Existence, uniqueness and asymptotic behavior of parametric anisotropic \$\(p, q\)\$ -equations with convection](#), *Appl. Math. Optim.*, **86** (2022), Paper No. 18, 18 pp.
- [35] S. Zeng, Y. Bai and L. Gasiński, [Nonlinear nonhomogeneous obstacle problems with multi-valued convection term](#), *J. Geometric Anal.*, **32** (2022), Paper No. 75, 14 pp.

- [36] S. Zeng, Y. Bai, L. Gasiński and P. Winkert, [Existence results for double phase implicit obstacle problems involving multivalued operators](#), *Calc. Var. Partial Differential Equations*, **59** (2020), Paper No. 176, 18 pp.
- [37] S. Zeng, L. Gasiński, P. Winkert and Y. Bai, [Existence of solutions for double phase obstacle problems with multivalued convection term](#), *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, **501** (2021), Paper No. 123997, 12 pp.
- [38] S. Zeng, V. D. Rădulescu and P. Winkert, [Double phase implicit obstacle problems with convection and multivalued mixed boundary value conditions](#), *SIAM J. Math. Anal.*, **54** (2022), 1898-1926.

Received December 2022; revised April 2023; early access May 2023.